

ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 1

ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES
№1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9556-2023-1>

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Theory, methodology and history of sociology. Methods of sociological research.

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Социальные структуры, социальные институты и образ жизни
Social structures, social institutions and way of life

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Социология социального сознания и социального процесса.
Sociology of social consciousness and social process

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МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Комил Каланов СИФАТЛИ СОЦИОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАРДА ИЖТИМОЙ КОНТРАСТНИНГ СОЦИОМАДАНИЙ КОНТУРИ.....	4
2. Аълохон Аликариева ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ТАЪЛИМ ОЛИШ СИФАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШНИНГ КВАЛИМЕТРИК ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	14
3. Моҳира Халикова ҲАЁТ ДАВОМИДА ТАЪЛИМ ПАРАДИГМАСИ АХБОРОТ ЖАМИЯТИНИНГ МУҲИМ ДЕТЕРМИНАНТИ СИФАТИДА.....	22
4. Раъно Исмайлова ОИЛАВИЙ ЗЎРАВОНЛИККА УЧРАГАН ШАҲСЛАРНИ ИЖТИМОЙ – ПСИХОЛОГИК-ҚЎЛЛАБ ҚУВВАТЛАШДА ҲИМОЯ ОРДЕРИНИНГ РОЛИ.....	30
5. Кахрамон Каюмов ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА КИЧИК ШАҲАРЛАР ИЖТИМОЙ ИНФРАТУЗИЛМАСИНИ БОШҚАРИШ ВА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	38
6. Бехзод Эрназаров МИЛЛИЙ ИДЕНТИКЛИК МУАММОЛАРИДА ХАЛҚ МАЪНАВИЯТИ ДИНАМИКАСИ.....	48
7. Хилола Хайдарова ШАҲАР ЭКОТИЗИМИДА БОШҚАРУВ ВА ИЖТИМОЙ ХОТИРА.....	54
8. Xasan Akramov SOG‘LOM TURMUSH TARZINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI XUSUSIDA AYRIM MULOHAZALAR.....	61
9. Хуршед Тошқулов СОЦИАЛ ДАВЛАТДА ИНСОННИНГ КУНДАЛИК ҲАЁТ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	67
10. Mohinur Ahmedova GLOBALLASHUV DAVRIDA AXBOROT SIYOSATI VA UNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI.....	75
11. Сабохат Каланова ЗАМОНАВИЙ АВЛОД ВА СОЦИОМАДАНИЙ ИДЕНТИКЛИКНИНГ ЎЗАРО АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ.....	84
12. Dilnoza Sultonova TALABALARDA IJTIMOIIY FAOLLIK KO‘NIKMAALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING MUHIM OMILLARI.....	92

ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

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GLOBALLASHUV DAVRIDA AXBOROT SIYOSATI VA UNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796910>

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola bugungi globallashgan dunyoda axborotni insonlar ongi, xayoti va jamiyatga ta'siri haqida. Ayni paytda yangi axborot texnologiyalarining ulkan imkoniyatlari axborotni geosiyosiy ta'sirning eng kuchli quroliga aylantirdi. Bugun dunyoda axborot eng xavfli qurolga aylandi u orqali har bir insonni ongiga tasir o'tqazish mumkinligi fanda isbotlandi.

Bugungi kunda kishilarga axborot orqali ta'sir ko'rsatishga xizmat qiluvchi vositalar strategik ustunlikka erishish vositasi bo'lib qoldi. Endilikda olimlar tomonidan axborot orqali ta'sir deganda axborot quroli (avvaldan muayyan maqsad sari yo'naltirilgan uzatiladigan, qayta ishlanadigan, yaratiladigan va qabul qilib olinadigan axborotni uzatish vositasi) vositasida insonlarning ongi va qalbiga ta'sir o'tkazish sifatida baholanmoqda. Zero, axborot orqali samarali ta'sir ko'rsatish muayyan maqsad targ'ibi yo'lida kishilarning fe'l-atvori, o'zligi, axloqi va ruhiyatiga, jamiyatdagi ma'naviy-ruhiy muhitga, jamoatchilik fikrining ijobiy yoki salbiy tomonga rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatishga qaratilgan maxsus axborotlarni yaratish va tarqatish kabi faoliyatlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot asri, axborotlashgan jamiyat, telekommunikatsiya, axborot tizimlari, siyosiy axborot, siyosiy monopulyatsiya.

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INFORMATION POLICY IN THE GLOBALIZATION AND ITS MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

ANNOTATION

This article is about today's globalized in the world information people to his mind and to life and to society effect about. At the same time, the enormous possibilities of new information technologies have turned information into the most powerful weapon of geopolitical influence. Today in the world information the most Dangerous to the gun became through it each one a person to his mind effect transfer possible in science proved.

Today, the means of influencing people through information has become a means of achieving strategic advantage. Now, scientists consider influence through information as an influence on the

minds and hearts of people by means of an information tool (a means of transmitting, processing, creating and receiving information directed to a specific goal). After all, effective influence through information includes activities such as creating and distributing special information aimed at influencing the character, identity, morals and spirit of people, the spiritual and spiritual environment in society, and the development of public opinion in a positive or negative direction in the way of promotion of a specific goal.

Key words: Information century, informed Society, Telecommunications, Information systems, political information, political manipulation.

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ИНФОРМАЦИОННАЯ ПОЛИТИКА В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ И ЕЕ ОСНОВНЫЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья о сегодняшнем глобализированном в мире информационном влиянии человека на его сознание, на жизнь и на общество в целом. В то же время огромные возможности новых информационных технологий превратили информацию в самое мощное оружие геополитического влияния. Сегодня в мире информация, наиболее опасная для оружия, стала передаваться через него каждому человеку в его сознании, эффект передачи возможен, научно доказано. Сегодня средство воздействия на людей с помощью информации стало средством достижения стратегического преимущества.

Сейчас ученые рассматривают влияние через информацию как воздействие на умы и сердца людей с помощью информационного инструмента (средства передачи, обработки, создания и получения информации, направленной на определенную цель). В конце концов, эффективное воздействие с помощью информации включает в себя такие виды деятельности, как создание и распространение специальной информации, направленной на воздействие на характер, идентичность, мораль и дух людей, духовную среду в обществе, а также на развитие общественного мнения в положительном или отрицательном направлении путем продвижения определенной цели.

Ключевые слова: век информации, информированное общество, телекоммуникации, информационные системы, политическая информация, политическая манипуляция .

INTRODUCTION

In today's, which is called the information age, various ways of fighting for the human mind and soul have been created, and information attacks are taking a leading place in this, along with the formation and development of social opinion through the medium of information [1, - P. 22]. "In the information society, new forms of mass communication will emerge, new paradigms will begin to form in social relations, ways of life and thinking, economy, politics, management, and it is necessary to prepare for this." If we focus here on the concept of information age and information society, in our opinion, the information age is a period in which the information factor takes a leading place in the daily activities of a person. Along with telecommunications, mass communication tools (telephone, fax, mobile phone) take a leading position [2, - P.25].

In the information society, educational and spiritual factors are leading with the help of information media. "Information society is the leading position of knowledge and information in productive forces and relations of production and in achieving growth of capital." In another definition, it is said that "Information society is a society in which sufficient conditions have been created for the preparation, processing, storage and dissemination of information in the socio-economic development" [3, -P.11].

Leadership in the development of information technologies and mass communication tools is becoming the most effective means of securing a dominant position in the current era. Western countries and Japan are getting closer and closer to completing the formation of the information society [4]. They have highly developed information systems and high technologies in the field of mass media. Therefore, it is not so difficult to estimate the dominance of information, in some cases, the dominance of the leader, in this case, we are not talking about some abstract leading states [5]. The era of the information society forms an infocracy - an elite with specific socio-political and economic interests. One of the new serious political problems, does not the information of the society increase the authoritarian tendencies? - is a question. One can imagine a situation where the ruling circles know everything and the others know nothing [6].

At the moment, the development trends in the field of information can be imagined that the political power obtained by the majority as a result of the concentration of information is not "directly implemented" [7]. The formed ruling elite will be a kind of "infocracy", and the source of its power will not be the services provided to the people, but the availability of great opportunities to use information. Information policy is the set of all public laws, regulations and policies that encourage, discourage, or regulate the creation, use, storage, access, and communication and dissemination of information. It thus encompasses any other decision-making practice with society-wide constitutive efforts that involve the flow of information and how it is processed [8, - P.6].

There are several fundamental issues that comprise information policy. Most prominent are public policy issues concerned with the use of information for democratization and commercialization of social life. These issues include, inter alia, digital environment, such as the digital divide, intellectual property, economic regulations, freedom of expression, confidentiality or privacy of information, information security, access management, and regulating how the dissemination of public information occurs. Certain categories of information are of particular importance for information policy. These include news information, health information, and census information.

Information policy is the central problem for information societies. As nations make the transition from industrialism to post-industrialism, information issues become increasingly critical [9, - P.214]. According to sociologist Daniel Bell, "what counts now is not raw muscle power or energy but information". While all societies have been to some extent based on information, information societies are almost wholly dependent on computerized information. As Marc Uri Porat, the first researcher to use the term "information policy", wrote: "The foundation of the information economy, our new central fact, is the computer. Its ability to manipulate and process information represents a profound departure from our modest human abilities". The computer's combination with telecommunications, he continued, posed "the policy problems of the future". The types of information policy can be separated into two different categories. It can be discussed in the short-term focus exclusively on information science. It can also have a much broader context in relation to different subjects and be within a larger time period, for example dating back to Roman civilization, the Bill of Rights, or the Constitution [10, - P.24].

The obvious reason for the need of information policy deals with the legal issues that can be associated with the advancement of technology. More precisely, the digitization of the cultural content made the cost of the copy decreasing to nearly zero and increased the illegal exchange of files, online, via sharing web site or P2P technologies, or off line (copy of hard disks). As a result, there are many grey areas between what users can and cannot do, and this creates the need for some sort of regulation. Today, this has led to the creation of SOPA (Stop Online Piracy Act). Information policy will mark the boundaries needed to evaluate certain issues dealing with the creation, processing, exchange, access, and use of information [11, - P. 38].

1. for avoiding risks (financial losses from incomplete and uncoordinated exploitation of information, wasted time, failures of innovation, and reputation loss);
2. for positive benefits, including negotiation and openness among those responsible for different aspects of information management
3. productive use of IT in supporting staff in their use of information

4. ability to initiate change to take advantage of changing environments

METHODOLOGY .

The term "information" is also used in the sense of "giving information", transmitting information and its distribution. Some researchers say that information is a message or information about something that is not known in advance. In any case, information is an important element, without which not only an individual, but also society cannot be imagined. The issue is its quality, content, tone and focus. Therefore, information is limited, fake, fast, current, etc. can be.

The five broad methodological strands that Rowlands identified are current tools for information policy study:

Classification: The tool demonstrates a wide range of issues and subjects on information policy. It helps research to understand the breadth of the subject. The published materials are reasonably well documented and described. It is also good for start-up literature review and research purposes [12, - P.38].

Identification of policy issues and options: This tool relies on inputs for information; for example, interviews and questionnaires targeting policy makers and other stakeholders. It is a commonly used in the studies of on-the-job policy makers in government or industry

Reductionism: The reductionist approach control factors to reduce ambiguity. The factors include constraining data collection, analysis and interpretation within the framework of a specific discipline [13].

Process-oriented research and cases studies: It provides detailed contextual analyses of particular events. It helps researcher to experience the policy process in semi-real situation and study its outcome.

At the same time, the enormous possibilities of new information technologies have turned information into the most powerful weapon of geopolitical influence. For this reason, there are concepts that evaluate the current policy of some developed countries as colonialism in a new form. It is no coincidence that terms such as "information neocolonialism", "information wars", "information expansion" are often used. But such considerations have not yet become absolute. Experts who are critical of the information society, such as Herbert Schiller, believe that the distribution of information for such forces in the ideological landfill is useful only when people (consumers of information) become herds [14,-P.194].

In general, in the conditions of today's ideological conflicts, mass media can be viewed in two ways: firstly, as a phenomenon affecting the minds of information consumers, and secondly, as a speech communication and information transmission act. Media caters to the aspirations and privacy of modern man, and is often designed to satisfy needs that appear in the unconscious emotions of man. The real task of such tools is to influence the minds of information consumers, to use them for their own interests, and the information wars are escalating. Various methods are used to achieve informational advantage by damaging the opponent's information, information processes and information systems [15, - P. 13].

Currently, there are many definitions in the mass media, some of them can be mentioned :

- information known to the population - means of conveying events and events in the world ; entities of the journalistic community that deliver information (news, investigations, etc.) to consumers for certain segments of the population ;

- regular dissemination of information (through print, television, film, audio recording, video recording) in order to morally confirm the values of society and ideological, political, economic or organizational evaluations, opinions and human behavior .

MAIN PART.

Modern globalization has significantly increased the influence of global mass media. Mass communication has become a serious tool of modern politics. The reason for this is due to the more serious role of public opinion in the current environment, which plays a decisive role in the formation of mass media. Currently, the general technology of manipulation affects the listeners through channels controlled mainly by people's minds. Thus, socio-political imaginary ideas enter the public

consciousness, they contain certain values and norms, and in most cases they are believed without critical reflection [16, - P. 35-36].

The goal of political manipulation is the false reality created by the mass media, which can fundamentally change the relationship between good and evil, truth and falsehood in people's minds. An important source of manipulation is that the media, because of their information monopoly, prioritize events. In order to strengthen or establish democracy, many people may feel the need for a free and independent media.

According to Edwin Baker, "democracy is impossible without a brilliant press. At least, that's what judges and legal commentators say. An independent and free media is especially necessary in times of transition. Free and independent media can take many forms, and freedom and independence, in turn, take many forms. This is about what the media should be like and what society should be like for democratic institutions to work [17, - P. 35-38].

Today, as the foundations of the information society, which is recognized as the third wave of civilization, are being formed, achieving the priority of our national values will ensure the stable development of our development. On the contrary, the information society, which does not rely on national values, moves away from moral factors under the influence of popular cultures. This is a fatal aspect. In this regard, the scientist Rahmon Kochkar approaches the issue as follows: "Today's sentence, which has named itself "information world", "informed society", is about one or another event in the world (it does not matter if it happened in history or yesterday - it does not matter) public information The more information and "instant news" that the media "finds" and distributes, the more abstract the real truth about that event becomes [18, - P.294].

The information policy of the state "is a specific type of life activity of people involved in the production, processing and distribution of information, representing the interests of the state and civil society, and ensuring creative, constructive communication between them and their representatives."

The objects of the state information policy are published mass media - newspaper, magazine and book publication, electronic mass media - television, radio, internet, as well as means of communication - telephone, pagers. "Information policy can be considered as a weapon of political influence and a means of achieving political goals: the subjects of information policy can influence people's mind, psyche, their morals and their activities within the framework of the interests of the state and civil society and personal interests with the help of information" [19, - P. 147].

In the context of the struggle for the human mind and heart, the concept of information policy is usually interpreted as a way of dealing with existing informational flows and resources of various institutional subjects (for example, state or state bodies that have their own views and interests in working with information, or individual organizations and agencies). In our opinion, information policy is an activity aimed at ensuring the stability of national interests by means of information resources, as well as against factors that threaten national security, and coordinates relations between state bodies and members of society [20].

Specific aspects of the globalization process are influence through information, information attacks, ideological and cultural expansion organized by countries claiming hegemony, cases of forcefully promoting the differences between the way of life of the West, which is materially provided for its culture and spirituality, and the people of the East, who are moving towards their development. Therefore, the unique aspect of the globalization process is considered as a period of struggle for human mind and soul.

Today, the means of influencing people through information has become a means of achieving strategic advantage. Now, scientists consider influence through information as an influence on the minds and hearts of people by means of an information tool (a means of transmitting, processing, creating and receiving information directed to a specific goal) [22]. After all, effective influence through information includes activities such as creating and distributing special information aimed at influencing the character, identity, morals and spirit of people, the spiritual and spiritual environment in society, and the development of public opinion in a positive or negative direction in the way of promotion of a specific goal [21, - P. 24-31].

The information policy of the state "is a specific type of life activity of people involved in the production, processing and distribution of information, representing the interests of the state and civil society, and ensuring creative, constructive communication between them and their representatives."

The objects of the state information policy are published mass media - newspaper, magazine and book publication, electronic mass media - television, radio, internet, as well as means of communication - telephone, pagers. "Information policy can be considered as a weapon of political influence and a means of achieving political goals: the subjects of information policy can influence people's mind, psyche, their morals and their activities within the framework of the interests of the state and civil society and personal interests with the help of information

In the context of the struggle for the human mind and heart, the concept of information policy is usually interpreted as a way of dealing with existing informational flows and resources of various institutional subjects (for example, state or state bodies that have their own views and interests in working with information, or individual organizations and agencies) [23, -P. 58]. In our opinion, information policy is an activity aimed at ensuring the stability of national interests by means of information resources, as well as against factors that threaten national security, and coordinates relations between state bodies and members of society.

Specific aspects of the globalization process are influence through information, information attacks, ideological and cultural expansion organized by countries claiming hegemony, cases of forcefully promoting the differences between the way of life of the West, which is materially provided for its culture and spirituality, and the people of the East, who are moving towards their development. Therefore, the unique aspect of the globalization process is considered as a period of struggle for human mind and soul [24, - P.149], [25].

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The historical development of mankind has created an opportunity for the emergence of various effective means and methods of influence in the media. As a result, in addition to the fact that the information factor took the leading place, it also created information contradictions, and this field also became a research object of some scientists [27].

According to A. Erkaev: "Due to the emergence of mass communication media - radio, cinema (later television, Internet, etc.), comic books, entertainment works, gramophone records (later video and audio discs) and other cultural consumer goods in an industrial way, "wholesale" production along with material goods, spiritual products were also standardized. Spiritual and cultural products have become consumer goods. Their form and content began to lose their local, regional and national features and characteristics. "

Russian expert in the field of the theory of information contradictions, doctor of technical sciences S.P. Rastorguev evaluates the concept of information war as "targeted informational influence of information systems in an open or hidden state in order to achieve a certain achievement in the material sphere." In this case, he says that the opposing side will have an advantage when the opposing side is busy repairing the temporary damage. According to the scientist, the information war does not differ from the usual war according to its characteristics and signs. The aggressor achieves subjugation by targeting the entire control system of the opposing party and wins

According to S. Rastorguev, there are also effective methods of organizing protection: reducing the extent of the existing risk; gradual loss of "unnecessary information"; establish tight control over their management system. According to the scientist, the strategy of using the information weapon should always be proactive. In his opinion, this is a very important result, not fully understood by the scientific community, which defines the forward-looking character of the information weapon and

helps to assess the capabilities of any powerful adversary. Thus, it can be said that the volume of information transmitted from one country to another is a measure of information aggression.

Today, developed countries strive to have a powerful propaganda system. For example, it is probably not for nothing that the US government spends 2.5 billion dollars a year on the promotion of its activities. Maybe France is not wasting 100 million francs a year on explaining its policy to the population?"

Recognizing that effective information policy is an important task in our country today, it is necessary to look for different ways of its implementation and choose the most appropriate way [27]. Therefore, researching the experience of developed countries helps to increase the efficiency of the work

UK information policy also has its own characteristics. In 1932, BBC radio broadcasts were distributed to foreign countries, previously it was carried out in English only to the countries of the British Empire (Australia, India, South Africa, West African countries and Canada). This service was called "BBC Empire Service" and was financed by the Foreign Office (Foreign Office) and served to convey the ideology of British lifestyle values to the population. It was a very novel approach to shortwave broadcasting for its time, and the researchers note that the "empire service" soon attracted a wide audience from different countries. In 1938, broadcasts were extended to Arab countries ("Arab Service") and Latin American countries ("Latin American Service"). At the same time, the "BBC Foreign Service" and later the "BBC Europe Service" were created, the European bulletins read in German, French and Italian. Until now, the financial support of all BBC radio broadcasts conducted abroad is under the responsibility of the Foreign Office [28, - P. 216].

In the field of news programs, the management of the BBC from 1988 began to implement a new strategy, with the aim of improving the skills of journalists and making them replace each other. At the same time, foreign bureaus were expanded and new departments with their own special correspondents appeared. Currently, the company broadcasts and programs in about 60 languages of the world. In particular, it has its own divisions in Central Asia and broadcasts in Uzbek.

According to the conclusions of a large number of American political scientists analyzing the structure of information policy in the United States, initially television had a special cooperative relationship with the country's top political leadership. The government guaranteed a huge income in exchange for supporting the main directions of its policies.

Si-SPEN (Cable Satellite Public Affairs Network), i.e. "Cable-satellite socio-political network", which was created in 1979 to keep the public informed about legislative activities, occupies a large place in the US information policy. While this channel broadcasts the Republican and Democratic congresses in full and without commentary, other commercial television companies cover them only during the evening shows.

Most western countries and the USA have developed the concept of "e-Government" ("electronic government") related to the information society. Under this name, governments around the world began to actively use information and communication technologies in order to improve the efficiency and quality of their services.

in the United States, 2.6 in Australia, 2.58 in Singapore, 2.52 in Canada and Great Britain, and 2.46 in Germany. This index shows that the country's development depends on the amount of investments in "digital" information and communication technologies (ICT).

CONCLUSIONS.

In short, any country, whether it is a powerful, industrialized country that has taken its rightful place in the world, or a developing country that has just gained its independence, is responsible for ensuring its security and paying serious attention to protecting its citizens from ideological threats. This situation serves to protect the state from various information and psychological threats. It should be noted that terms such as "information war" and "psychological war" are used in a number of Western countries. In Uzbekistan, the phenomenon called "ideological threat" and terms such as "information war" and "psychological war" are essentially very close to each other. While the leading foreign countries are paying great attention to protecting themselves from the same informational and psychological wars, the fact that independent Uzbekistan is also putting national security issues at the

forefront in the presence of ideological threats is a political activity carried out in the interests of the citizens of our country, ensuring security and stability in the region, that is, the peace of mankind.

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ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 1

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